

ANALYSIS OF THE TEACHER OF CHEMISTRY AND DIDACTIC REQUIREMENTS APPLICABLE TO HIM

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Abstract. *In this article, the didactic demands of the modern chemistry teacher are analyzed, the theoretical and practical issues of their systematization based on the structure, content and modern approaches of the modern chemistry teaching process are highlighted. The author's definition of the modern chemistry teacher is given.*

Keywords: *teaching process, structure, content, teaching chemistry, improving chemistry lessons.*

Taking into account the requirements of the educational process and the needs of chemistry teachers, in this article we aimed to develop methodical recommendations on ways to improve the chemistry lesson and to activate the activity of students in chemistry lessons.

Solving the complex tasks of education and upbringing of young people depends to a great extent on the teacher, his ideological beliefs, professional skills, talent and culture.

As stated in the state strategy on education improvement, the teacher is the architect of the spiritual world of the young person, the trusted person of the society, the society entrusts the teacher with the dearest and most valuable children, its hope, its future. This is a very noble and very difficult profession, which requires constant creativity, unceasing thinking, great generosity of spirit, love for children, and hard work. The teacher won the deep gratitude and respect of the people with his selfless and enlightening work in the field of education of the young generation.

Teachers are the pride of our country, the reliable support of the nation in educating young people. In our country, the role of the teacher, increasing his reputation and attention is always being taken care of. It is impossible to solve any of the issues related to school life without the participation of the teacher.

It is necessary for a chemistry teacher to understand that teaching, that is, teaching, is a very complex and responsible profession. The teaching profession requires serious preparation. The teacher is entrusted with the responsible task of educating people who fully respond to the needs of life and are worthy of the era of acceleration and market economy.

Trust in teachers is a major issue right now, and the key to overcoming many of our school shortcomings lies in trust in teachers.

As Professor A.A. Makarenko noted, the teacher should be given a lot of trust and freedom. The teacher should not be a mechanical follower of the instructions given from above, but should be free like a poet, like an artist, teach with love and knowledge. Only then can he be a true teacher of the subject he teaches.

A teacher is a person who has a creative approach to the educational process, who has the right to implement the educational methods and tools that he finds acceptable and which ultimately give high results. The diploma given to the teacher by the state gives him the right to search for effective methods of education and upbringing.

The quality of school chemistry education mainly depends on the teacher. In order not to fall behind the requirements of the times, the teacher should not be satisfied with his existing

knowledge, but should update, supplement and enrich it. A teacher can have the right to teach only if he studies tirelessly and learns independently. Because knowledge in the field of science, technology, and pedagogy is updated and expanded more and more. Therefore, the teacher should always be sought. Pupil's respect and follow teachers who know their subject well, who love their profession, who have a wide scope, who are entrepreneurs, who can find a way to please them, who can satisfy their needs for knowledge.

Since the teacher is a professional pedagogue and educator of the future generation, he should not only know his field and subject well, he should also know well the ways of conveying knowledge to the minds of students (effective educational methods and technologies). A teacher must be confident in his own strength and ability.

A chemistry teacher must be committed to his duties and responsibilities. He loves students from the bottom of his heart, has a sincere attitude towards them: disciplined, obedient students, enthusiastic students who don't listen, perceptive students, and relatively less intelligent students; He should love the busy student and the lazy student equally, and should have a sincere communication with all of them. The teacher should not touch the students' sense of honor, should not even think of humiliating them.

Innovative, creative approach to education can sometimes be met with resistance. Introducing innovation requires skill and courage from the teacher. A teacher should be an optimist (look at life and the future with hope). He should be sure of the education he is giving, the educational methods and tools he is applying, and their educational effect. It is necessary not to be afraid of difficulties in the educational process, not to be discouraged. Overcoming adversity takes courage. If the students are satisfied with the new educational forms, methods and tools implemented by the teacher, if they are interested, listen carefully and do certain work, this is a sign of good work. The creative search of the teacher is considered successful only if he can develop the creative abilities of the students.

At the same time, based on the description of the subject, there are didactic requirements specific to the chemistry teacher. They include the teacher's perfect mastery of the chemistry experiment and the technique of its implementation, and the ability to use them effectively in meeting the state standards. This is the implementation of the scientific principle of teaching while being aware of the achievements of the chemical science and industry of the present time.

The author imagines a modern chemistry teacher as a highly educated specialist with a broad profile who can provide the quality of education to meet the requirements of state standards, using the achievements of information technologies in the teaching process, with a deep understanding of not only chemical knowledge, but also pedagogical and psychological laws. In addition to these, there are a number of other requirements, the fulfillment of which should ultimately serve to activate the cognitive activity of students. This topic requires a separate discussion. Thus, the didactic demands placed on a modern chemistry teacher are structured according to the types of activities according to their descriptions, and each of them has its own place and important didactic task in the educational process. It is the need of the hour to constantly improve these types of activities.

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